

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION FOR DETERMINING THE CONSOLIDATION PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER TAPES WITH PA 6 MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

One of the key aspects for the successful and economic manufacturing of parts with fiber-reinforced thermoplastics is the profound understanding of the consolidation process. In order to model and optimize this process some material properties need to be determined. In this paper three different carbon fiber reinforced tape materials, all with a Polyamid 6 matrix, are characterized with respect to their consolidation properties in a comparative study. Based on the model of intimate contact development, the surface roughness and the viscosity are selected as main parameters of interest. The surface of the tapes is analyzed with a tactile and an optical method and the characteristic values R_a and R_z are determined. An experimental setup is presented to determine the fiber-matrix viscosity of the tapes by conducting squeeze-flow experiments. In order to evaluate the fiber-matrix structure of the tapes, micrographs are produced and analyzed with respect to predefined criteria. The experiments reveal a large difference in surface roughness and squeeze-flow viscosity between commercially available tapes, which indicates a large difference in the development of intimate contact during consolidation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics with thermoplastic matrix systems have been more and more used in industrial applications during the past years. Therefore the processing of thermoplastic prepreg materials such as tapes and organo-sheets has been a focus of academic and industrial research. The use of thermoplastic prepreps reduces the cycle time and the use of potentially hazardous materials such as solvents and epoxy-based resin systems at manufacturing sites.

Whereas aircraft-industry thermoplastic prepreps such as PEEK with an AS4 fiber have been used and investigated since the 1980s, little attention has been paid to materials with industry-grade fibers and engineering plastics as matrix material. In recent years a variety of materials has been developed, which for example consist of a combination of Polyamides (PA) with industry-grade carbon fibers. These materials, a growing market and the further development of manufacturing techniques have contributed to lower material costs for thermoplastic prepreps. Simultaneously the laser-assisted automated fiber or tape placement (AFP) technology has been emerging, which not only allows to layup tape material which is consolidated in a successive autoclave process, but also for the in-situ consolidation [2]. Consolidation processes in autoclaves or hot-presses provide high pressure over a long period of time. Therefore these processes are suitable to produce a high interlaminar bond strength even if there is a variation in tape properties. In comparison to these traditional processes, AFP technologies, which aim for the in-situ consolidation of the material without a successive post-consolidation step in an autoclave, demand for uniform and well-known tape-properties, because the applied pressure in these processes is much lower and the time for consolidation is limited to less than one second. Different states of fiber materials along the process-chain of carbon fiber reinforced plastics with corresponding process technologies are summarized in Figure 1.

An increasing variety of available materials in combination with the breakthrough of processes, which are sensitive to material properties such as AFP, demand for increasing efforts in material testing with respect to consolidation characteristics.

Therefore in this study we address the following questions: which are the relevant properties of tape material in order to describe and model consolidation? How can these properties be determined? We answer those questions by conducting and evaluating three different tests with three different materials in a comparative study. Namely we apply two different methods for surface characterizations, we conduct squeeze-flow experiments two determine the fiber-matrix viscosity and we use the analysis of micrographs to describe the fiber-matrix structure of the tapes. Two of the materials are commercially available materials; the third non-commercial material is selected to illustrate some distinct differences with respect to the surface structure of the tape.

Figure 1: Material states and corresponding processes of thermoplastic tape materials

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND SELECTION OF TESTING METHODS

In this section we specify more precisely the process of consolidation and we use two models from literature which are employed for the description of consolidation. We refer to these models to identify the key properties of the tapes, which we are looking at.

We define consolidation as the process of combining two thermoplastic surfaces under the application of temperature and pressure over a defined period of time in order to maximize the interlaminar bond strength between these surfaces. Development of interlaminar bond strength comprises of two simultaneously occurring phenomena: both surfaces are brought into contact and intimate contact

develops. Once intimate contact is established a bonding process, which is called healing, occurs. According to this model the degree of interlaminar bond strength D_B [4] is defined as:

$$D_B = D_{IC} D_h \quad (1)$$

During healing the chain like molecules of the polymer diffuse across the interface of both surfaces which are in contact. The progression of this healing process is quantified by the degree of healing D_h . Healing depends on the type of polymer [4]. As the polymer for all materials in this study is PA 6, we focus on the first term of the equation above, the development of intimate contact. Intimate contact is quantified by the degree of intimate contact D_{IC} which can be expressed by the following equation [4]:

$$D_{IC}(t_c) = D_{IC,0} \left[1 + 5 \left(1 + \frac{w_0}{b_0} \right) \left(\frac{a_0}{b_0} \right)^2 \int_0^{t_c} \frac{P_{app}(t)}{\eta(T(t))} dt \right]^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (2)$$

The equation above reveals the main parameters, which influence the development of intimate contact. The pressure P_{app} in equation 2 is a process parameter and independent from the material used. The parameters $D_{IC,0}$, w_0 , a_0 and b_0 are geometric parameters which can be obtained from the surface structure of the tapes. Therefore, the first parameter we aim to investigate is the surface roughness of the selected materials. Different approaches have been used to obtain the parameters w_0 , a_0 and b_0 from measured surface profiles. In [5] the parameters are measured from micrographs, [6] proposes a fractal Cantor set based description to describe the surface, [7] fits the parameters to experimental results from actual consolidation experiments and [8] fits the parameters to measured surface profiles. Due to this variety of methods we choose a more general approach for the surface-characterization by measuring the characteristic values for surface roughness R_a (average roughness height) and R_z (mean waviness height). High values for R_a and R_z indicate a rough surface and therefore suggest that a longer consolidation process is necessary to obtain full intimate contact. The material's viscosity η is a function of the process temperature and is highly dependent on the material. Even if the matrix of all tapes is known as PA 6, the viscosity is often modified for manufacturing purposes of the tapes. Furthermore, for the modelling of the consolidation the mixed fiber-matrix viscosity is more relevant than the neat resin viscosity. Therefore, our second goal is to determine the temperature-dependant fiber-matrix viscosity of the tape material. In order to do so, we conduct squeeze-flow experiments. From the results of these experiments the fiber-matrix viscosity can be derived using a flow model.

As mentioned in the introduction, the fiber-matrix distribution of the tapes is important for the determination of suitable parameters for consolidation processes. For example the temperature distribution and heat penetration depends on the thermal conductivity of the materials which again depends on the fiber matrix structure. Therefore, as a third method for the characterization of tape materials we propose the analysis of micrographs according to predefined criteria. The micrographs are also helpful to interpret the results of the surface characterization and the squeeze-flow experiments.

3 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Materials

In the presented study three different types of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced tapes from different manufacturers with a PA 6 matrix denoted as tape 1 (T1), tape 2 (T2) and tape 3 (T3) were investigated. Tape 1 is Ultratape B3WC12 by BASF, tape 3 is Celastran CFR-TP PA6-CF60 by Celanese, which are both commercially available. Tape 2 is a sample material which is still under development. The material is selected for this study to illustrate some differences in surface properties.

For the analysis of micrographs all samples were taken from different areas along the width and the length of the tapes.

Samples for the squeeze-flow experiments were manufactured in a hot-press. One plate with the dimensions of 290 mm x 330 mm x 2.1 mm was produced for each material. The tapes were heated to 250 °C and subsequently pressed at 5 bar for 5 minutes. Afterwards they were cooled with a cooling rate of 15 °C/min.

3.2 Surface Characterization

For the analysis of the tape surfaces two methods are compared. First the surface roughness was determined with a tactile measurement using a Mahle perthometer with a 3 μm diamond head. Second we employed a Keyence 9700 laserscanning microscope, which is an optical method.

For each material 5 samples with a size of 25 mm x 35 mm were cut. The tapes were fixed to a polished aluminium plate using a double-sided adhesive tape. The samples were aligned using a sample-press for microscopes.

For the optical measurement in a first step, images were taken using a 20x magnification. For each sample a length of 5 mm perpendicular and 5 mm parallel to the fiber direction was scanned. In total for each sample 96 individual images were taken and stitched for analysis with a Keyence software. In a second step 10 surface profiles and roughness measurements were conducted for each sample perpendicular to the fiber direction.

For the tactile measurement the same samples were tested at 5 individual positions perpendicular to the fiber direction for a measured length of 5.6 mm.

3.3 Squeeze-Flow Experiments

A squeeze-flow describes the deformation of a material between two approaching surfaces. More precisely it describes flows, in which a material is compressed between two boundaries and thus squeezes out in a direction perpendicular to the direction of compression [9]. In squeeze-flow experiments, the flow of fibers and matrix due to pressure, which is applied by the two surfaces of the testing fixture is similar to the flow occurring during consolidation processes. Therefore, the squeeze-flow method to determine the fiber-matrix viscosity is preferred to experiments in a cone and plate rheometer in this study.

In the presented study we use a squeeze-flow-model, which was developed for process simulation of thermoplastic wound parts [10]. For this model a no-slip boundary condition is assumed to exist at the free and the bonding surface. Furthermore an isothermal process, a constant viscosity, a constant compaction force, a constant fiber volume fraction and an incompressible fluid (a void-free laminate) is assumed. From this model the following equation can be derived to evaluate the fiber-matrix viscosity η_{MF} :

$$\eta_{MF} = \frac{5 F t (h_i^2 h_f^5)}{8 L_i W_i^3 (h_i^5 - h_f^5)} \quad (3)$$

with

- F: applied force
- t: time for compression
- L_i : initial length of the sample
- h_i : initial thickness of the sample before compression
- h_f : final thickness of the sample after compression
- W_i : initial half width of the tape

For the experiments the samples are cut to an initial size of 40 mm (L_i) x 20 mm ($2 \times W_i$). The specimen's dimensions are determined for each sample individually. The initial thickness (h_i) is measured using a micrometer gauge.

The specimens are placed between two steel plates, which are attached to a universal testing machine. The entire setup is located in a thermo-chamber (Figure 2 left). Before heating, the samples are placed on the lower steel-plate and no force is applied by the upper plate. During heating and testing the sample's temperature is controlled using several thermocouples to ensure isothermal testing at the desired temperature. Once the temperature is equilibrated the upper plate is lowered until contact. During the tests a constant compaction force of 100 N is applied for 60 s. Tests are conducted for

225 °C, 240 °C and 260 °C. The displacement of the plates is measured using an optical videoextensometer. The results are fitted to a semi empirical Arrhenius relation of the form:

$$\eta_{MF} = A e^{A/T} \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Experimental setup for squeeze-flow experiments: upper and lower plate in thermos chamber (left) and sample (right)

3.4 Method and Criteria for the Analysis of Micrographs

For the analysis of micrographs 10 samples with a width of 2 cm perpendicular to the fiber direction were taken from each material. The specimens were embedded in an epoxy resin and grinded with silicon carbide paper. A dispersion with abrasives between 6 μm and 1 μm was used for successive polishing steps. At each sample 5 measurements were conducted according to predefined criteria, which are described in the following paragraph. An Olympus BX41M microscope was used for the analysis.

For the analysis seven criteria are proposed, which are summarized in Figure 3. For the first criteria a greyscale distribution was evaluated to determine the fiber area ratio and the porosity ratio (criterion 1 and 2) with respect to a predefined material envelope. These values can be correlated with the actual initial fiber volume content and the initial porosity of the material. The next criteria aim to evaluate the maximum (criterion 3) and the minimum tape thickness (criterion 4). As the development of intimate contact is dominant in the surface-near domains of the tapes a profound characterization of the fiber-matrix structure in this area must be considered. Therefore, we define the boundary area of the tape as the difference between the maximum and the minimum tape thickness. In this region we determine the fiber area ratio in the surface area (criterion 5) similarly to criterion 1. As some tapes do not show a particularly homogenous fiber distribution, we aim to describe fiber bundle patterns by size and extension in criterion 6. In this criterion we measure the periodicity of repeating patterns. Finally we evaluate if the fiber-matrix distribution and the amount of pores is symmetric to the mid-plane of the tape. An uneven distribution might be induced by the impregnation process of the tapes and can be important for further processing e.g. the energy absorption in laser assisted tape laying depends on the matrix-content near the tape surface [11]. Also an unsymmetrical distribution of fibers may hint at a different surface-roughness at the top and the bottom of the tapes.

Criteria	Principle	Example
1: fiber area ratio 2: porosity		
3: maximum tape thickness		
4: minimum tape thickness		
5: fiber area ratio in surface area		
6: fiber bundle patterns: periodicity		
7: symmetry of top and bottom side (qualitatively)		

Figure 3: Overview of criteria for analysis of micrographs

4 RESULTS

4.1 Surface Characterization

From the measured surface profiles two characteristic values R_a and R_z for surface roughness were determined. Whereas R_a describes the mean roughness of a surface R_z is more sensitive to single peaks in the surface structure. The measured length for the optical measurement was 5 mm and for the tactile

measurement it was 5.6 mm. The cut-off wavelength for both methods was 0.25 mm. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Measured Entity	Unit	Tape 1	Tape 2	Tape 3
<i>Perthometer R_a</i>	μm	3.41 ± 1.27	2.56 ± 0.35	1.51 ± 0.16
<i>Perthometer R_z</i>	μm	21.10 ± 7.65	15.19 ± 3.96	9.21 ± 0.09
<i>Optical R_a</i>	μm	2.06 ± 0.24	0.87 ± 0.20	0.54 ± 0.06
<i>Optical R_z</i>	μm	17.92 ± 0.24	9.63 ± 1.51	9.74 ± 1.77

Table 1: Results of roughness measurement with perthometer and optical measurement

The measurements indicate that T3 has the smoothest surface structure (smallest R_a and R_z) followed by T2 and T1. According to the theory of intimate contact development T3 will allow for the fastest establishment of full contact. Whereas the absolute values of the optical measurement differ from the results of the tactile measurement, both methods lead to the same conclusion in a relative comparison between different materials. The characteristic values R_a and R_z vary with the measured length and cut-off wave length which is chosen for the analysis [12]. Therefore it is necessary to choose identical test parameters (surface area under investigation, measured length, cut-off-wavelength), when using roughness measurements for the selection of materials and for quality inspection.

In addition to the identification of the roughness parameters 3D profiles of the tapes were taken to learn more about the reasons for the identified difference in surface roughness and its implications. The images and the corresponding height profiles of the materials are shown in Figure 4. The analysis of T1 (which also has the largest R_a and R_z values) reveals the existence of local areas where single roving bundles are not covered by the matrix. In other regions fibers are fully covered, however fiber marks are visible in the height profile of the surface. In comparison the surface of T3 (which has the smallest R_a and R_z values) exhibits some smaller grooves, but in general there are no exposed fibers and no fiber marks visible. In comparison to T1 and T3, T2 shows a fundamentally different surface structure. The analysis of the height profile reveals a periodic pattern of plateaus and dents. These patterns are independent from the tape's fiber orientation. Despite this pattern the characteristic surface roughness parameters suggest a rather smooth surface. There are no visible fiber marks. Additional roughness measurements with the optical method revealed almost identical characteristic roughness values for measurements in the fiber direction and in the transversal direction. As the surface structure is independent from the fiber orientation, the patterns must be induced by the manufacturing process of the tape.

Figure 4: Micrograph images of tape surfaces (T1-T3) on the left side and corresponding 3D surface-profiles on the right side for a measured area of 5 mm x 5 mm with 20x magnification

4.2 Squeeze-Flow Experiments

The conducted squeeze-flow experiments were used in a first step to characterize the compaction and the accompanying flow behavior of the materials. In a second step the characteristic fiber-matrix

viscosity can be derived, which may be used for the comparison of different materials or as input for the modelling of intimate contact development according to equation 2.

Figure 5 shows the dimensional change of the samples before and after the experiment. The width of the unidirectional samples increases by approximately 50% at 225 °C which is only slightly above melting temperature of PA 6. The length of the sample remains constant and there is no matrix flow in fiber direction. The fiber-matrix mixture only flows in the transversal direction, perpendicular to the main fiber orientation. This indicates that the squeeze-flow model for the viscosity may be applied [10].

Figure 5: Samples of T3 before and after testing at 225 °C

Figure 6 illustrates the change of sample thickness for T3 during compaction for three different temperatures and the corresponding compaction force. The desired compaction force of 100 N could be reached after 6-8 s. Therefore, the assumption of a constant compaction force cannot be met over the entire testing period. The reason for the relatively slow equilibration of the force is the flow of the specimen. As soon as the upper plate establishes contact with the specimen, the material shows a large deformation and the controller of the testing machine must adjust the distance between upper and lower plate. However, in order to determine the order of magnitude of the viscosity for the purpose of process design this approach is sufficient, as a force level of 80-90 N was reached after 2 seconds whereas the thickness of the sample only changed by 5-9% in the same time.

For T1 and T3 (T2 was not tested in this experiment) the fiber-matrix viscosity was calculated using equation 3. The results and fitted curves to an Arrhenius relation for both materials are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Example for the change of sample thickness of tape 3 for three different temperatures (left) and resulting viscosities for tape 1 and tape 3 with fitted curves (right)

Both materials show a similar decrease of viscosity with increasing temperature. Even though both materials consist of carbon fibers with a PA 6 matrix, the viscosity of T3 is approximately twice as high compared to the value of T1. The fiber-matrix viscosity, which is determined with the described method, depends on a combination of three properties of the tape material: the fiber volume content, the arrangement of fibers in the tape and the properties of the neat PA 6 resin. The fiber volume content and fiber-matrix structure will be investigated in the next section. The viscosity of the neat resin of the investigated materials is not known, however, the viscosity can be modified by the manufacturers to facilitate the impregnation during tape production. In order to identify the reason for the difference in fiber-matrix viscosity it is necessary to characterize the neat resin of both tapes.

4.3 Analysis of Micrographs

The results of the analysis of the micrographs according to the predefined criteria from *section 3.4 Method and Criteria for the Analysis of Micrographs* are summarized in Table 2. The fiber area content and void content (criterion 1/criterion 2) do not differ significantly. However, these results need to be validated with measurements of fiber volume content by acid digestion. The measured fiber area content in the tapes boundary area (criterion 5) varies between 16 and 24 %. T3 which showed the smoothest surface without visible fiber marks also has the smallest fiber volume content near the surface area. The evaluation of criterion 6 reveals large roving bundles which can be clearly distinguished from each other in T1. T3 also exhibits a clear roving structure, but fiber bundles are less wide. The transition between adjacent fiber bundles in T3 is also less distinct. In the analysis of T2 no fiber bundle patterns can be identified.

Criterion	Unit	Tape 1	Tape 2	Tape 3
1	%	40.4 ± 5.9	40.5 ± 6.6	41.0 ± 4.4
2	%	1.1 ± 0.9	1.9 ± 1.4	1.5 ± 1.4
3	µm	186.0 ± 6.7	221.0 ± 22.5	151.7 ± 5.6
4	µm	151.4 ± 18.4	175.5 ± 23.4	129.4 ± 8.6
5	%	18.1 ± 10.3	25.0 ± 10.6	18.9 ± 8.5
6	µm	339.0 ± 102	-	194.12 ± 70
7	-	yes	yes	yes

Table 2: Results of micrograph analysis

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper we aimed to address the following two questions: Which are relevant material properties of tapes in order to describe consolidation? How can these properties be determined?

In the presented study we have identified the surface roughness and the fiber-matrix viscosity in combination with the fiber matrix distribution as process relevant parameters for thermoplastic tapes. Furthermore we have presented three methods to characterize three different materials with a PA 6 matrix with respect to these material properties.

A tactile and an optical method for the measurement of the surface roughness were used to determine characteristic surface roughness values. The absolute values of the measurement results, which were obtained by the haptic measurement differ from those of the optical method. However, in a relative comparison between different materials, which is relevant for material selection and quality insurance in industrial applications, both methods lead to the same conclusions. The analysis of the 3D surface scans reveals distinct surface structures of the three tapes under investigation. T1 has a relatively smooth surface with locally visible fiber marks. T3 shows no fiber marks and a closed matrix surface. The unique surface structure of T2 is characterized by a pattern of plateaus and dents. These regular patterns extend in the fiber and in the transversal direction of the surface, whereas for most tapes, there is a dominant orientation of grooves parallel to the fiber direction. Current models which describe the intimate contact development [5, 6] only account for a 2D flow in the tape's plane perpendicular to the fiber direction. These models cannot account for the flow in the fiber direction, which occurs during consolidation of T2 due to this 3D surface patterns.

The existing models for the development of intimate contact (e.g. equation 2) which describes a fundamental step of the consolidation process can be used to assess the properties of T1 and T3. According to this model, the smooth surface of T3 is favourable for the establishment of full contact. On the other hand the measured viscosity of T3 is approximately twice as high as the viscosity of T1, which will prolong the process of contact establishment. At this point more experimental work is needed to investigate the role of the correct measurement of viscosity for consolidation. In this study we determined the squeeze-flow viscosity of the material which takes into account the influence of fibers in the polymer matrix. This viscosity therefore depends on the global fiber volume content of the samples. The tapes under investigation show an unhomogenous fiber-matrix structure. The analysis of micrographs reveals that in all materials the fiber volume content in the boundary layers is clearly smaller (approximately 20%) than the global fiber volume content of the tapes. In the literature some authors, who have used the concept of intimate contact for the evaluation of consolidation, have referred to the fiber-matrix viscosity e.g [5, 7, 13] whereas [8] has used the viscosity of the neat resin. However, these authors do not refer to the actual fiber matrix-structure of the tapes which were used in their experiments. Therefore, further research is needed to investigate if the neat resin viscosity or the fiber-matrix viscosity is more appropriate depending on the fiber-matrix structure of the tapes.

The presented study shows that a combination of different methods is needed to appropriately characterize tape-materials. Also the further development of consolidation models is needed to take into account the more complex surface structure and the less homogenous fiber-matrix structure of new tape materials.

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